

¹⁴C measurements on Santa Catalina petrosal bones

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Samples	Lab. code	Material
<i>CSN'13_CEF6</i>	-	Petrosal bone
<i>CSN'13_CEF8</i>	-	Petrosal bone
<i>SCT'15_TIUF21_5005</i>	FI4767, FI4775	Petrosal bone
<i>SCT'15_TIUF21_5006</i>	Fi4763, Fi4765	Petrosal bone

Table 1 Samples fractions prepared for ¹⁴C-AMS measurements.

Sample preparation

Before any radiocarbon measurement, the sample to be dated has to be prepared in order to remove all the possible contaminations and to isolate the original carbon.

Figure 1 Bone samples subjected to preparation.

As a first step, for each of the samples, the portion chosen for the measurement was first mechanically cleaned using a scalpel to remove the most external layers and then crushed. Since a translucent material, probably indicating the use of some consolidating product, was present on the samples, we decided to clean the selected powdered material by several extractions in chloroform before proceeding with collagen collection. Four extractions in chloroform were applied. Then, collagen was extracted following the so-called Longin method:

- complete demineralization in aqueous 0.5M HCl at room temperature for about 24 hours, at least;
- purification in aqueous 0.1M NaOH at room temperature for 2 hours;
- further bath in 1M HCl at room temperature for 2 hours to remove any CO₂ possibly absorbed from atmosphere during the previous step;
- gelatinization of the collagen-based acidified solution (pH ~3) at 80°C.

During this procedure, collagen cannot be extracted from samples *CSN'13_CEF6* and *CSN'13_CEF8*. Actually, after the pre-treatment, the two samples showed significant reddish residues (see Figure 2), which were insoluble in acidic solution (such a behaviour suggests that the original bone matrix might have replaced by other minerals).

Figure 2 Reddish residues collected after pre-treatment of samples *CSN'13_CEF6* and *CSN'13_CEF8*.

After pre-treatment, carbon was extracted from *SCT'15_TIUF21_5005* and *SCT'15_TIUF21_5006* samples as gaseous CO₂ by combustion in elemental analyser

(CHN Thermo Flash1112) and then converted to graphite, i.e. solid carbon, exploiting the reaction of carbon dioxide with hydrogen (with iron as catalyst). Two separate fractions from the same cleaned sample were independently combusted and graphitised (see Table 1 for the laboratory codes).

Results

Graphite pellets were measured by Accelerator Mass Spectrometry (AMS) at the dedicated beam line of the Tandem accelerator at INFN-LABEC laboratory in Florence.

